

Evaluation Results and Logs

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3DPaV Ventilator	1	4
A.R.M.E.E. Ventilator	3	5
Ambovent	2	4
Automatic Rescucitator	1	3
Breath4Life	1	4
CAM Ventilator	2	4
CoRescue	1	4
CoronavirusMakers	1	4
COVID19 Respirador (Vaccharini)	1	1
COVID-19 Ventilator	2	3
crowdsourced-ventilator-covid-19	2	4
Cuirass-Ventilator	2	4
DIY-Beatmungsgerät [Respirator]	2	3
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Ferraru F15 Ventilator	2	5
Fluxtronic	2	4
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INSPIRE - OpenLung	3	5
Johnny Lee's Papr	2	4
Low-Cost Open Source	2	4
MakAir	3	5
Mechanical Ventilator Milano (MVM)	1	6
MIT E-Vent	1	5
MUR (Minimal Universal Respirator)	2	4
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Nabil Ventilator	3	4
Open Breath Italy	2	5
Open Source Ventilator - OpenLung BVM Ventilator	2	3
Open Source Ventilator Project	1	4
OpenVent-Bristol V3.0	3	5
OpenVentilator	2	3
OpenVentilator (PopSolutions)	2	4
OperationAIR	1	4
People's Vent	3	5
Project Inspiration	3	4
Protofy Team OxyGEN	3	6
ReesistenciaTeam	1	1
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Rice OEDK Design: (2019) ApolloBVM	3	4
Rice OEDK Design: ApolloBVM	3	4
Venti Builders	1	4

-----Project Name : 3DPaV (3D Printer as Ventilator)

- ODRL – 1

Comments

Files available but not collaborative (ref - <https://www.thingiverse.com/thing:4566892/files>)

- OTRL – 4

Comments

Design files shared, Prototype built (ref -

https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=h3B8AIHpvJY&ab_channel=KevinWhelan)

-----Project Name : A.R.M.E.E. Ventilator

- ODRL – 3

Comments

Collaborative documentation under open source license

Stable version of Ventilator released. (ref -

https://github.com/MillionVentilators/ARMEE_Ventilator_1.0/tree/master/stable)

- OTRL – 5

Comments

Design files published (ref -

https://github.com/MillionVentilators/ARMEE_Ventilator_1.0/tree/master/stable)

Reliable Manufacturing process documented (ref -

https://github.com/MillionVentilators/ARMEE_Ventilator_1.0/blob/master/documentation/Build_Instructions.md, <https://docs.google.com/document/d/1ZnPGnA-GKtFLsJEDVVLLKqNAKSk3q6F47YqvtuoJVXw/edit#heading=h.omo5a34z4o5n>)

----- Project Name : Ambovent

- ODRL – 2

Comments

Collaborative documentation shared under open source license (ref - <https://github.com/AmboVent-1690-108/AmboVent>)

- OTRL – 4

Comments

Design files shared (ref - <https://github.com/AmboVent-1690-108/AmboVent>)

Prototype built (ref - <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=4f6rNCI8iv4>)

----- Project Name : Automatic Resucitator

- ODRL – 1

Comments

Files shared, but not editable/collaborative (ref - <https://www.thingiverse.com/thing:4239988/files>)

- OTRL – 3

Comments

Design files available, no evidence of working prototype (ref -

<https://www.thingiverse.com/thing:4239988/files>)

----- Project Name : Breath4Life

- ODRL – 1

Comments

Documentation under free license, not fully collaborative.

(<https://viralresponse.io/+makilab/breathoflife-in-belgium/files>)

- OTRL – 4

Comments

Design files available, prototype built (ref - https://youtu.be/S_W9AvPNN1o)

----- Project Name : CAM Ventilator

- ODRL – 2

Comments

Documentation published under OS license and collaborative. (ref - <https://github.com/Arcus-3d/cosv/>)

- OTRL – 4

Comments

Design files published. Prototype built. (ref -

https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=FMebChgRhXM&ab_channel=Arcus-3D)

----- Project Name : CoRescue

- ODRL – 1

Comments

Cannot find files, license claimed to be OS, but not in list from SPDX

- OTRL – 4

Comments

Prototype available, no other documentation available. (ref - <https://corescue.org/wp-content/uploads/2020/04/VENT-40-002-BIN-Ventilator-Demonstration-Video-Rev.-002.mp4>)

----- Project Name : CoronavirusMakers

- ODRL – 1

Comments

Documentation not collaborative, but published with free OS license.

- OTRL – 4

Comments

Design files are published as pdf, but prototype is built. (ref - <https://youtu.be/7SLfA67qTE8>)

----- Project Name : Covet-19: Team Breathe Easy

Comments

Rejected, NC license, no collaborative documentation

----- Project Name : COVID-19 Rapid Manufacture Ventilator (BVM)

- ODRL – 3

Comments

OpenVent Bristol, Stable version released with open license. (ref - https://github.com/Open-Vent-Bristol/Open-Vent-Bristol_MCU)

- OTRL – 5

Comments

Design files shared, manufacture process documented and optimized for mass production. (ref - <https://www.instructables.com/COVID-19-Rapid-Manufacture-Ventilator-BVM-Ambubag-/>)

----- Project Name : COVID19 Respirador (Vaccarini)

- ODRL – 1

Comments

Documentation under free OS license, but not collaborative. (ref - <https://github.com/vaccarini/covid19respirador>)

- OTRL – 1

Comments

Product idea available, but no design files. (ref - https://docs.google.com/document/d/1z06rEOX_Jf6soLEfomvGs7rINXRS_1dPuQfoMjTGBHs/edit)

----- Project Name : COVID-19 Ventilator

- ODRL – 2

Comments

Documentation published under free OS license, and collaborative (ref - https://github.com/kaiem/COVID-19_Ventilator_DIY_Prototype)

- OTRL – 3

Comments

Design files published, only Proof of Concept (untested prototype) is available. (ref - <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=GDeOzsM8-c&feature=youtu.be>)

----- Project Name : crowdsourced-ventilator-covid-19

- ODRL – 2

Comments

Documentation published under free OS license, and collaborative (ref - <https://github.com/Crowdsourced-Ventilator-Covid-19/crowdsourced-ventilator-covid-19>)

- OTRL – 4

Comments

Design files published, prototype built. (ref - <https://youtu.be/sNcdRJmJqwU>)

----- Project Name : Cuirass-Ventilator

- ODRL – 2

Comments

Documentation published under free OS license, and collaborative (ref - <https://github.com/jps2000/Cuirass-Ventilator>)

- OTRL – 4

Comments

Design published, Prototype is built. (ref - <https://youtu.be/EyCMbskHRjY>)

----- Project Name : DIEGO ventilator

Comments

Rejected, resources seem to have been deleted, no data found regarding the project. (ref - <https://www.iit.it/iit-vs-covid-19/diego-ventilator>)

----- Project Name : DIY-Beatmungsgerät [Respirator]

- ODRL – 2

Comments

Documentation published under free OS license, and collaborative (ref - <https://github.com/DIY-Beatmungsgerat/diy-beatmungsgeraet>)

- OTRL – 3

Comments

Design files available, no evidence of prototype. (ref - <https://github.com/DIY-Beatmungsgerat/diy-beatmungsgeraet/tree/master/hardware>)

----- Project Name : DP Ventilator

- ODRL – 1

Comments

Documentation available but not collaborative. (ref - <https://hackaday.io/project/171890-dp-ventilator>)

- OTRL – 4

Comments

Design files published, prototype built. (ref - <https://youtu.be/GMOeC1Nxmx0>)

----- Project Name : Ferraru F15 Ventilator

- ODRL – 2

Comments

Documentation published under free OS license, and collaborative (ref - <https://github.com/icub-tech-iit/ventilator-F15>)

- OTRL – 5

Comments

Design files published, prototype available, optimized design for production. (ref - https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=0cS7hDUI7wY&ab_channel=IstitutoItalianodiTecnologia, <https://www.iit.it/web/guest/fi5-pulmonary-ventilator>)

----- Project Name : Fluxtronic

- ODRL – 2

Comments

Documentation published under free OS license, and collaborative (ref - <https://github.com/fluxtronic-medical/Fluxtronic>)

- OTRL – 4

Comments

Design files published, prototype built. (ref - <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=dyl--hyxr6U&feature=youtu.be>)

----- Project Name : gVent

- ODRL – 2

Comments

Documentation published under free OS license, and collaborative (ref - <https://github.com/COSMIC-medical/gVent>)

- OTRL – 4

Comments

Design files published, prototype built. (ref - <https://youtu.be/yVxmjUQLIBw>)

----- Project Name : INSPIRE - OpenLung

- ODRL – 3

Comments

Documentation published under free OS license, multiple versions released. (ref - <https://github.com/Inspire-Poli-USP/Inspire-OpenLung>)

- OTRL – 5

Comments

Several units, upwards of 500 have been produced. (ref - <https://www.polisp.br/category/noticias/noticias-do-inspire>)

----- Project Name : Johnny Lee's Papr

- ODRL – 2

Comments

Documentation published under free OS license, and collaborative (ref - <https://github.com/jcl5m1/ventilator>)

- OTRL – 4

Comments

Design files published, prototype built. (ref – <https://youtu.be/n57u1NvXBgw>)

----- Project Name : Low-Cost Open Source

- ODRL – 2

Comments

Documentation published under free OS license, and collaborative (ref - <https://github.com/jcl5m1/ventilator>)

- OTRL – 4

Comments

Design files published, prototype built. (ref – <https://youtu.be/n57u1NvXBgw>)

----- Project Name : MakAir

- ODRL – 3

Comments

Documentation published under free OS license, multiple versions released. (ref - <https://github.com/makers-for-life/makair>)

- OTRL – 5

Comments

Manufacture process optimized for easy production, claimed on press release. (ref - <https://makair.life/2020/04/30/revue-de-presse-du-30-avril-2020/>)

----- Project Name : Mechanical Ventilator Milano (MVM)

- ODRL – 1

Comments

No files published

- OTRL – 6

Comments

CE approval received. (ref - <http://mvm.care/>)

----- Project Name : MIT E-Vent

- ODRL – 1

Comments

No collaborative files for hardware, software published under free OS license.

- OTRL – 5

Comments

Design optimized for production and Manufacturing process documented. (ref - <https://emergency-vent.mit.edu/>)

----- Project Name : MUR (Minimal Universal Respirator)

- ODRL – 2

Comments

Documentation published under free OS license, and collaborative (ref - <https://github.com/LeClubSandwichStudio/MUR>)

- OTRL – 4

Comments

Design files published, prototype built. (ref – https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=ySPmER19sPk&t=40s&ab_channel=LeClubSandwichStudio)

----- Project Name : MVP

- ODRL – 2

Comments

Documentation published under free OS license, and collaborative (ref - https://drive.google.com/drive/folders/1XTNc5_pEWI1ATr-WRFbC4TW5NCqKutzC)

- OTRL – 3

Comments

Design files uploaded, no evidence of prototype.

----- Project Name : Nabil Ventilator

- ODRL – 3

Comments

Documentation published under free OS license, stable versions released. (ref - <https://github.com/Nabilphysics/ventilator/>)

- OTRL – 4

Comments

Design files published, prototype built. (ref - <https://youtu.be/ixd7w3A6EIQ?list=PLWOXOpFr-Z50Q3X0qPz6WNfCwyVcnYaeS>)

----- Project Name : Open Breath Italy

- ODRL – 2

Comments

Documentation published under free OS license, and collaborative (ref - <https://ohwr.org/openbreath/lungventilator/tree/master/CAD>)

- OTRL – 5

Comments

Design optimized, collaborated with manufacturing partner. (ref - <https://riverdi.com/blog/openbreath-and-riverdi-join-forces-to-produce-low-cost-lung-ventilators/>)

----- Project Name : Open Source Ventilator - OpenLung BVM Ventilator

- ODRL – 2

Comments

Documentation published under free OS license, and collaborative (ref - <https://gitlab.com/open-source-ventilator/ventilator/OpenLung>)

- OTRL – 3

Comments

Design files available, no evidence of prototype.

----- Project Name : Open Source Ventilator Project

- ODRL – 1

Comments

Documentation available, but not collaborative. Software released on OS license. (ref - <https://simulation.health.ufl.edu/technology-development/open-source-ventilator-project/bill-of-materials/>)

- OTRL – 4

Comments

BOM published, and cad drawings in pdf, prototype built. (ref - <https://simulation.health.ufl.edu/technology-development/open-source-ventilator-project/in-the-media/>, <https://simulation.health.ufl.edu/technology-development/open-source-ventilator-project/build-test-instructions/cad-drawings/>)

----- Project Name : COVID-19 Rapid Manufacture Ventilator (BVM)

- ODRL – 3

Comments

OpenVent Bristol, Stable version released with open license. (ref - https://github.com/Open-Vent-Bristol/Open-Vent-Bristol_MCU)

- OTRL – 5

Comments

Design files shared, manufacture process documented and optimized for mass production. (ref - <https://www.instructables.com/COVID-19-Rapid-Manufacture-Ventilator-BVM-Ambubag-/>)

----- Project Name : OpenVentilator

- ODRL – 2

Comments

Documentation published under free OS license, and collaborative. (ref - <https://github.com/OpenVentilator/OpenVentilator>)

- OTRL – 3

Comments

Design Files published, no evidence of prototype. (ref - <https://github.com/OpenVentilator/OpenVentilator/tree/master/hardware>)

----- Project Name : OpenVentilator (PopSolutions)

- ODRL – 2

Comments

Documentation published under free OS license, and collaborative. (ref - <https://github.com/popsolutions/openventilator>)

- OTRL – 4

Comments

Design files available, prototype built. (ref - https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=8HZpF1QwhUk&ab_channel=PopSolutionsDigitalCooperative)

----- Project Name : OperationAIR

- ODRL – 1

Comments

Documentation available, but not collaborative. (ref - <https://osf.io/mn7xq/>)

- OTRL – 4

Comments

Design files available, prototype built. (ref - <https://www.operationair.org/>)

----- Project Name : People's Vent

- ODRL – 3

Comments

Documentation published under free OS license, collaborative and stable version released. (ref - <https://github.com/CohenLabPrinceton/pvp>)

- OTRL – 5

Comments

Assembly process documented, prototype built, mentioned as designed for minimal reliance on supply chain. (ref - <https://www.peoplesvent.org/en/latest/overview/overview.html>)

----- Project Name : Project Inspiration

- ODRL – 3

Comments

Documentation published under free OS license, collaborative and stable version released. (ref - <https://github.com/CombatCovid/TU-Delft-PI-Emergency-Ventilator>)

- OTRL – 4

Comments

Design files available, prototype built (ref - <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=SHrkCkhW2U0&t=63s>)

----- Project Name : Protofy Team OxyGEN

- ODRL – 3

Comments

Multiple versions released. (ref - https://github.com/ProtofyTeam/OxyGEN/tree/master/oxygen_M)

- OTRL – 6

Comments

Already approved by spanish academy. (ref - <https://www.oxygen.protofy.xyz/>)

----- Project Name : ReesistenciaTeam

ODRL – 1

Comments

Files not published. (ref - <https://gitlab.com/reesistencia/reespirator-beagle-touch>)

OTRL –

Comments

Only product idea is available.

----- Project Name : respiArt

ODRL – 2

Comments

Stp file of design published. (ref - <https://github.com/artur-iluk/respiArt>)

OTRL – 4

Comments

Prototype built. (ref - https://youtu.be/BUc_ID-wEiQ)

----- Project Name : RespiraWorks

ODRL – 2

Comments

Documentation published under free OS license, and collaborative. (ref - <https://github.com/RespiraWorks/Ventilator>)

OTRL – 3

Comments

Design files available, prototype built but untested. (ref - <https://github.com/RespiraWorks/Ventilator>)

----- Project Name : Rice OEDK Design: (2019) ApolloBVM

ODRL – 3

Comments

Stable versions released, Documentation under free OS license and collaborative. (ref - <https://github.com/apollobvm/apollobvm>)

OTRL – 4

Comments

Design files published. Prototype available. (ref - <https://oedk.wildapricot.org/apollobvm/>)

----- Project Name : Rice OEDK Design: ApolloBVM

Comments

Stable versions released, Documentation under free OS license and collaborative. (ref - <https://github.com/apollobvm/apollobvm>)

OTRL – 4

Comments

Design files published. Prototype available. (ref - <https://oedk.wildapricot.org/apollobvm/>)

----- Project Name : Venti Builders

ODRL – 1

Comments

Documentation is under free OS, no evidence of 3d files. (ref - https://gitlab.com/venti_ventilator/venti)

OTRL – 4

Comments

Prototype build. (ref - https://gitlab.com/venti_ventilator/venti)